

Changes in Fish Consumption Pattern and Consumer Perception: A Case Study of the MV X-Press Pearl Ship Disaster, Sri Lanka

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The MV X-Press Pearl cargo ship, which was carrying many noxious chemicals, substances, and low-density polyethylene pellets, caught fire when it arrived off the coast of Colombo on May 19, 2021, creating numerous negative impacts on both environment and humans. Understanding the key factors that influence consumer behavior in the aftermath of such environmental disasters can assist fishery industries in becoming more resilient in the face of such catastrophic events. The purpose of this study is to evaluate perceptions and behaviors regarding fish consumption patterns among Sri Lankans following this disaster. This study was carried out using a pretested and structured online questionnaire using Google Forms from May to July 2021. Data were collected from 546 households across Sri Lanka and analyzed using Microsoft Excel and SPSS. Prior to the incident, 53.7% of respondents rely on marine fish as their primary protein source. Eighty-five point three percent (85.3%) of them had stopped or reduced their fish consumption as a result of the incident. Among those who stopped eating fish, the majority (22.4%) indicated that they would avoid eating marine fish for at least a year, and 4.4% said they would never eat fish again. 44.8 % of them indicated that they would move to eggs as their primary protein source, 27.6% to chicken, 17.6% to fresh water fish, and 12% to vegetable protein sources. The Wilcoxon Signed Rank Test of pre and post fish consumption amount was significant ($Z = -17.0, p = 0.000$), showing a significant reduction in marine fish consumption as a primary protein source. Our key findings indicate that, regardless of socio-demographic variables, there is a significant decline in fish consumption patterns as a result of the incident. Untrustworthy information about this incident has also harmed people's perceptions of consuming marine fish. To reduce the spread of false news, 38.5% ranked awareness through reputable organizations as the most important, followed by long-term research on fish and disseminating findings to the general public (30.4%), and immediate dissemination of research-based findings to the general public (29%). Accordingly, careful and efficient response to the incident in disseminating research-based findings is crucial to minimize the negative impacts on consumers and people engaged in the marine fish supply chain.

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